

Study of Government Policy on the Development of Sustainable Tourism Villages in the Borobudur Area of Central Java

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Abstract:- This study aimed to identify and examine government policies toward developing their village into a sustainable tourism village in the Borobudur Magelang area, Central Java. The method used is a qualitative and quantitative approach, data collection techniques through field observations, Forum Group Discussion, questionnaires, and in-depth interviews with local leaders and government. The data analysis method used is descriptive statistical analysis. In addition, the results presented contain clear information and can ease get information. The results of this study indicate that local government policies to develop sustainable tourism villages need to involve the local government, the tourism industry, and the community in formulating policies and village development programs. It needs to be done because when the local community feels and enjoys the positive impact of tourists visiting and even staying in their village as a tourist village, to increase economic, social, and improving community welfare, they will continue to maintain the town as a tourist village and will even try to increase their income through community innovation products as typical the villages to offering the visitors.

Keywords;- Policy, Government, Borobudur.

I. INTRODUCTION

One area that to considering to have strong potential to be developed as an ecotourism destination is the area around the Borobudur Temple area, Magelang at Center Java Province. Borobudur Temple is one of Indonesia's prime destinations for tourist arrivals, having an area of 2,119.21 square meters.

The development of tourist villages in the Borobudur Temple tourist area continues to increase. Every town has the Balkondes that can conduct tourists to stay longer in the National Strategic Area (KSN) that the government has set. Foreign tourists who come to Magelang Regency are not only amazed by the Temple of the Borobudur but also by the development in the temple area because almost all villages in the Borobudur District area are changing so fast.

Based on the background described above, the problem in this research is How is the government's policy toward the sustainable development of Tourism Villages in the Borobudur Magelang area, Central Java?

II. MATERIAL AND METHOD

This research uses a descriptive statistical analysis method and frequency. The results presented contain clear information, and readers can ease get information [1].

The scope of this research is quantitative descriptive research, and the technique used is to distribute questionnaires to tourism village managers. In addition to obtaining deeper data, interviews by several sources such as village heads, community leaders, and tourism village managers.

III. THEORY

a) State Of The Art

The development of sustainable tourism in rural areas is strong influencing by the acceptance and resilience of the community in tourism development. As in Kampung Naga and Kampung Sinarresmi, they consider that the village is not a tourist attractiveness, but their acceptance as hosts and tourists as guests. Meanwhile, Sade Desa considers the area a tourist attraction, so tourist visits are an opportunity to increase the local community's economy by commercializing traditional dances [2]. Village Development Strategy around Borobudur Temple Based on the Typology of Tourism Potential. This study maps the typology of villages around Borobudur temple based on their tourism potential, identifies factors that play a role in developing tourism potential based on known typologies, and determines known development strategies. [3]

b). Tourist Village

A tourist village is a form of integration between attractions, accommodation, and supporting facilities by presenting as a structure of community life where they integrate with applicable procedures and traditions. Rural tourism is tourism that consists of the overall experience, natural attractions, heritage of a community, and unique elements that can attract tourists [4]

c. Tourism Village Development

The tourism development policy carried out by the government is toward developing tourism as a mainstay and superior sector in a broad sense to be able to become one of the foreign exchange-earners, encourage the economy, increase regional income, empower the people's economy, expand employment opportunities and business opportunities and improve people's welfare by maintaining national personality, religious values as well as the preservation of the function and quality of the environment [5]

The principles of tourism development are 1. Recognize, support, and promote community-owned tourism 2. Involve community members from the start in every aspect 3. Promote community pride 4. Improve the quality of life 5. Ensure environmental sustainability 6. Maintain local character and culture uniqueness 7. Help develop cross-cultural learning 8. Appreciate cultural differences and human dignity 9. Distribute benefits fairly among community members 10. Contribute a determined percentage of community project income [6]

The basis for developing a tourist village is an understanding of the character and capabilities of the elements in the villages, such as environmental and natural conditions, social culture, community economy, the layout structure, historical aspects, community culture, and buildings, including indigenous knowledge (knowledge and abilities). local) owned by the community. [7]

d. Village Development Goals

The purpose of developing a tourist village is to preserve the natural environment and increase economic growth in an area so that by implementing the concept of a tourist village, it becomes a form of tourism that is friendly to the environment in the future [8]

e. Tourism Village Development Level

The level of development of a Tourism Village as a tourism product by into 3 (three) stages: Potential, Developing, and Advanced.

Potential Stages level a Tourism Village is Still, in the form of potential that develops to become a tourist destination, the development of tourism the facilities and infrastructure are still limited. They are still few community awareness tourists visiting has not grown/is still low too.

Developing Stage, at this strengths are Tourism Village is specified by characterized as follows: already known and visited by tourists, there has been the development of tourism infrastructure and facilities, jobs and economic activities have begun to be created for the local community, public awareness

of tourism potential begin to grow, still, require assistance from related parties (government or private).

Forward Stages, a Tourism Village is characterized as follows: the community is fully aware of the tourism potential with its development, has become a well-known tourist destination and is visited by many tourists, the facilities and infrastructure as well as tourism facilities are adequate, the community is independent and able to manage self-supporting tourism businesses (HR, Organizational Products, etc.), capable of self-help promotion and marketing as well as developing a network of cooperation with external parties, can become a pilot model for the development of other tourist villages.[9]

IV. RESULT

a) Overview of Borobudur Area

The Borobudur area is an administrative located in Magelang Regency and has interesting natural attractions, some of which are Punthuk Setumbu Hill. From the mount, the tourist can see a light mist with the silhouette of the Borobudur Temple and rows of trees. For nature lovers who challenge adrenaline, rafting or white water rafting activities along Kali Oya and Kali Progo are favorites for tourists visiting Magelang.

1) A Brief History of Borobudur Temple

The Borobudur history describes the construction of the Borobudur Temple beginning in the 8th and 9th centuries at around 800 Masehi during the Syailendra dynasty. Building the Borobudur took tens to hundreds of years and was completed during the reign of King Samaratungga in 825. The Syailendra dynasty was a Mahayana Buddhist, and there was adherence to Shiva Hindus around the Borobudur.

The splendor of Borobudur had disappeared for centuries because it was under a layer of soil and volcanic ash which was then overgrown with trees and shrubs to resemble a hill. The return of the fame of Borobudur Temple occurred during the time of Thomas Stamford Raffles as Governor-General on the island of Java in 1811. They heard that there was a large building hidden deep in the forest near the village of Bumisegoro. And in the end, it was designated as a World Heritage Site by UNESCO in 1991.

2) The shape of the Borobudur Temple

As the largest Buddhist temple and monument in the world, Borobudur Temple has a structure like a Punden Berundak, which is getting smaller and smaller with four stairs in each cardinal direction. Borobudur Temple has a length of 121.66 meters, a width of 121.38 meters, and a height of 35.40 meters. According to Buddhist philosophy, the level structure of the Borobudur Temple is an imitation of the universe for the wheel of life. There are three levels in the design of the Borobudur Temple, namely:

The Kamadhatu: The lower part of the temple symbolizes the underworld that describes human behavior that is still worldly desires.

Rupadhatu: The middle part of the temple symbolizes the intermediate nature, and describes the behavior of humans who have started to leave worldly desires but are still in the real world.

Arupadhatu: The upper part of the temple symbolizes the upper realm, depicts the intangible element, and is a sign of the level that has left worldly desires.

The stones in Borobudur Temple come from rivers around Borobudur total volume of about 55,000 cubic meters, equivalent to 2 million pieces of stone.

The Borobudur temple is a large monument of Buddhist architecture in Java, Indonesia. The history of the Borobudur Temple also records several functions in parts of the temple.

4) Borderline:

The boundaries of the Borobudur Village area are North Boundary, Bumiharjo Village, and the Progo River flow is directly adjacent to Mungkid District. East Boundary, Wanurejo Village, South Boundary: Tuksongo Village and West Boundary are Karangrejo Village and Wringing Putih Village. Borobudur village consists of 20 hamlets scattered around the Borobudur temple.

5) Geographical Condition

Geographically, Borobudur Village is in the form of plains, and in the middle, there are three hills, namely Jaten Hill, Borobudur Hill, and David Hill. While in the western part of Michigan's hamlet, there is a mount. Mahitan people usually call it Mount Bakal. In Borobudur Village, two rivers also form the village boundary: the Sileng River in the south and the Progo River in the north.

6) Religion

The majority of the population of Borobudur Village is Muslim. The Muhammadiyah congregation mainly lives found in the west and north of the temple. The Nadhatul Ulama congregation mainly lives found in the east and south of the temple. In addition, there are also Catholics whose church locate in the hamlet of Ngaran I.

V. DISCUSSION

The results of the study indicate that the development of tourist villages by the Borobudur Regional Village government plays a prime role in providing support and promoting tourist villages in the Borobudur area. The village government has played a role in involving the community in planning and developing tourist villages so that the existence of tourist villages in the Borobudur Area Village contributes to improving public welfare. The complete research results show in table 4.1, and the explanation is below too.

No.	Statemen	Ave.	Category
1.	Local governments recognize, support, and promote community-owned tourism	3,5	Very Playful
2.	Local governments involve community members from the start in every field	2,92	role
3.	Local government always promotes community pride	3,33	Very Playful
4.	The local government is making strong efforts to improve the quality of life through the tourism village.	3,33	Very Playful
5.	Local governments make strong efforts to ensure environmental sustainability	3,33	Very Playful
6.	Local governments make strong efforts to maintain the unique local character and local culture	3,25	Very Playful
7.	Local governments make strong efforts to help develop cross-cultural learning	3,16	role
8.	Local governments make strong efforts to help develop cross-cultural learning	3,83	Very Playful
9.	The local government makes powerful support to distribute benefits fairly among community members.	3,08	role
10.	The local government makes powerful support to contribute the specified percentage of community project income	3	role
	Average overall rating	3,29	Very Playful

a) Recognize, support, and promote community-owned tourism

Based on the table above, the results of the research show that the respondents' responses to the local government's statement acknowledging, supporting, and promoting tourism owned by the community in the development of tourist villages in the Borobudur Area Village are an average of 3.5. That means the local governments play a very important role in providing recognition and support and promoting tourism. Tourism development is a way or activity to advance a village through a tourist attraction or its potential so that the tourist attraction is better and more attractive and can increase the attractions for tourists to visit it.

Sustainable tourism needs supporting by good planning, reflecting three dimensions of interest, the local community to improve the quality of life, the tourism industry, and the environment (natural resources). [10]

b) Involve community members from the start in every aspect

TABLE I. RESEARCH RESULT

Based on the results of this study, the number of respondents' responses to local government statements involving community members from the beginning in each field was an average of 2.92. It means that the development of tourist villages in the Borobudur area, Magelang district, is supported by community involvement in every aspect of tourism village development. That means that the village head involves the community in developing tourism in the Borobudur area is sustainable. The fundamental thing to make tourism development run well and well managed is to facilitate the involvement of local communities in the development process and also optimize the value of social and economic benefits from tourism activities for local communities as well as an equally important position in tourism development, apart from the government. and private industry. [11]

c) Promote community pride

Based on the table of research results, the number of respondents' responses to the statement that local governments always promote community pride is an average of 3.33. shows that the development of tourist villages in the Borobudur area is supported by community pride promotion activities by the head of the Villages. Tourism promotion activities introduce the potential of the Villages to increase the desire to visit the promoted village. Now, social media is effective and efficient in promoting the attractiveness of tourist villages. Tourism industry products which include tourist attractions, ease of travel, facilities and facilities, and promotions, affect the development of tourism in a tourism village. [12]

d) Improve the quality of life

Based on table I above, the result shows that the number of respondents' responses to the statement that the local governments are making efforts to improve the quality of life through tourist villages is an average of 3.33. The meaning of that number is the village head plays a fundamental to the community in the Borobudur and improve the quality of life in tourist villages. So that local people feel the positive impact of the existence of a tourist village in improving the welfare of the local community. tourism development is to improve the quality of life of local communities by providing opportunities for them to be involved in tourism development. [13]

f) Ensuring environmental sustainability

Based on the Ensuring Environmental Sustainability Tab, the results of the research above show that the number of respondents' responses to the statement that local governments are making efforts to ensure environmental sustainability is an average of 3.33. The result means that the development of tourist villages in the Borobudur area needs to be instrumental in guaranteeing ecological sustainability around tourist objects. The village government's activities are in the form of protecting tourists by providing convenience in providing information, the village government involving local communities in tourism activities, and the village government making policies related to the protection and maintenance of traditional culture and arts in the community. Tourism development needs to pay attention to several things as follows:

1. protect tourists and provide convenience in providing information.

2. Local people should participate in tourism activities and enjoy equitably economic, social, and cultural benefits.

3. Tourism policy should be directed in such a way as to improve the standard of living of the local community.

4. Directing Tourism policies and activities in a series of:

(a) respect, protection, and maintenance of the rich heritage of art, archeology, culture, monuments, holy places, museums, and historic places;

(b) the survival and development of cultural products, traditional arts, and folk arts [14]

g) Preserving the unique local character and culture

➤ Preserving the unique local nature and culture

Based on the table above, the result of the study shows that the number of respondents' responses to the statement that local governments are making efforts to maintain unique local character and culture is an average of 3.25. It means that in the development of tourist villages in the Borobudur area, the village head plays a very instrumental role in maintaining the unique local character and culture. According to respondents, the considering of the village head has a very instrumental role in developing a tourist village by paying attention to environmental and ecological principles, being sensitive to traditions, customs, and culture that exist in the community, and maintaining the natural, social and cultural resources in the development of a tourist village. Environmental and ecological principles, sensitivity to local cultural and religious traditions, and placing and involving every community in tourism development in their villages. [15]

h) Help develop cross-cultural learning

Based on the table above, the result of the study shows that the number of respondents' responses to the statement that local governments are efforts to help develop cross-cultural learning is an average of 3.16. It means that in Developing tourist villages in the Borobudur area, the village government / Lurah plays a powerful role in helping to develop cross-cultural learning. The activities carried out by the Village Head/Lurah in the Borobudur area are maintaining relations between tourists and the local community, providing fair benefits for the local community, and working together to protect the environment. Community-based Rural Tourism Development (CBT) is tourism aware of social and cultural sustainability, including the environment. Community-based tourism takes into account aspects of cultural and environmental sustainability realization development of sustainable tourism through a more balanced relationship between tourists and local communities in the tourism industry. The balance in question includes, among others, community ownership status, fair profit sharing, cultural factor relationships based on mutual respect, and joint efforts to protect the environment. [16]

i) Respect for cultural differences and human dignity

Based on the table above, the result of the study shows that the number of respondents' responses to the statement that the local government is trying hard to respect cultural differences and human honor is an average of 3.83. It means

that the local government, especially the Head of the Village, plays very instrumental in efforts to respect cultural differences and human honor. It happens because of consideration of the Village Head/Lurah to collaborating with the local community in developing a tourist village by respecting local cultural and religious traditions. Tourism development that blends with community activities will impact the sustainability of natural resources, culture, industry, local wisdom, and other local resources owned by local communities. In the end, local people get economic benefits and improve their welfare. [17]

(j) Distribute the benefits fairly among the members of society

Based on the table above, the result of the study shows that the number of respondents' responses to the statement that the local government is trying to distribute benefits fairly among community members is an average of 3.08. It means that respondents think that the local government, in this case, the village head, plays a role in distributing fair benefits among members of the community group. The respondent believes that the village head creates employment opportunities for the local community. The respondent also believes that the village head has a continuation of the culture and resources and provides direct economic benefits to the local community. The form of community-based tourism development has advantages such as; the creation of employment opportunities for the community, supporters of cultural preservation, a more secure belief in the continuation of local community resources, and the existence of economic benefits that directly the community will enjoy it. [17]

k) Contributing funds from a percentage of project income to the community

Based on the table above, the result of the study shows that the number of respondents' responses to the statement that the local government is trying to distribute benefits fairly among community members is an average of 3.08. It means that respondents think that the local government, in this case, the village head, plays a role in distributing fair benefits among members of the community group. The respondent believes that the village head creates employment opportunities for the local community. The respondent also believes that the village head has continuation of the culture and resources and provides direct economic benefits to the local community. The form of community-based tourism development has advantages such as; the creation of employment opportunities for the community, supporters of cultural preservation, a more secure belief in the continuation of local community resources, and the existence of economic benefits that directly the community will enjoy it. [17]

The overall respondent's assessment of the policy of the Village Head / Lurah in the Borobudur Area is, on average, 3.29. It means that the regional government or Lurah plays a very important role in the sustainable development of tourism villages. This result is strongly supported by some of the opinions of the experts described above, where they express their belief that sustainable village development needs to involve local communities so that the resources owned by the tourist village, such as social, cultural, customs, and natural environment are maintained. The preserved resources will be

used as an attraction for tourists to visit and revisit a tourist village, especially the Borobudur area, which can increase the income/economy of the local community.

VI. CONCLUSION

Based on the explanation above, local government policies, especially village heads toward the development of sustainable tourism villages, need to involve not only the government itself and the tourism industry but also need to involve the community in formulating policies and village development programs. It needs to be done because when the local community feels and enjoys the positive impact of tourists who visit and even stay in their village as a tourist village, such as economic and social improvement, and ultimately their welfare increases, the community will continue to maintain the villages as a tourist village and will even try to increase their income through products that offered to visitors. With the existence of a tourism village that is managed sustainably, it will increase the creativity and innovation of the tourism village community to produce innovative and creative works whose materials come from local villages. In addition, the resources owned by the tourist village will be well maintained, such as the environment, local wisdom, and socio-cultural and community customs that are unique and attractive to tourists.

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